

Teacher Development As Influenced by Teacher Evaluation System

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Abstract. The study investigated the teacher evaluation system in private schools and their influence on teacher development in Davao City. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data collected were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r, and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of teacher evaluation systems in terms of professional conduct is frequently manifested; student achievement and specialized skills were sometimes manifested; classroom evaluation and use of technology were rarely manifested, thus, moderately extensive; likewise, the extent of teacher development in terms of coursework and advanced degrees, awards and recognition and leadership and service roles are often manifested, while, published work and research is rarely manifested, thus, moderately extensive. There was a significant correlation between teacher evaluation systems and teacher development. Domains of teacher evaluation systems in terms of classroom evaluation, student achievement, professional conduct, use of technology, and specialized skills significantly influenced teacher development. Future research may examine how contextual factors, such as school culture and leadership, affect the relationship between teacher evaluations and subsequent growth.

KEY WORDS

1. teacher evaluation systems
2. teacher development
3. classroom evaluation

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1. Introduction

The implementation of effective Teacher Evaluation Systems in Private Schools and their influence on Teacher Development faces several unique challenges. Firstly, many private schools may have limited resources for professional development and teacher evaluation, making it challenging to establish comprehensive and continuous assessment systems. The cost associated with hiring external evaluators or implementing sophisticated evaluation software can strain school budgets. Secondly, ensuring that teacher evaluation systems align with the school's mission and educational philosophy can be complex. Private schools often take diverse educational approaches, and finding evaluation methods that accommodate these distinct philosophies while promoting professional growth can be challenging. Across the globe, the potential for subjectivity in teacher evaluations can be a concern in private schools, where relationships among staff, students, and parents may be closer and more intertwined. Ensuring

that evaluations are fair, unbiased, and transparent is paramount to maintaining trust within the school community. Moreover, the pressure to demonstrate the positive impact of teacher evaluation systems on teacher development and, subsequently, student learning outcomes can be considerable. Private schools may face external scrutiny from parents, accreditation bodies, or funding sources, all of which demand evidence of the effectiveness of these systems (Stevens et.al., 2023). Ensuring equitable access to development programs is crucial (Gist, 2022). As in many educational systems, concerns about subjectivity and potential bias in teacher evaluations can arise. Ensuring that assessments are conducted fairly and transparently is an ongoing concern. Access to technology and digital resources for data collection and analysis may be limited in some areas of the Philippines. Ensuring that teacher evaluation systems are technologically feasible and accessible is a challenge. Achieving cultural sensitivity in assessments and evaluations is a vital consideration. Adhering to national policies and standards for teacher evaluation while allowing flexibility for localized approaches can be complex. Ensuring policies are effectively implemented at the school level is a persistent challenge (Jung, 2023). Several challenges related to Teacher Evaluation Systems and their influence on Teacher Development are prevalent in the Philippine education system. These challenges are influenced by the specific context and dynamics within the Philippine educational landscape. Many schools face resource constraints, particularly in rural and economically disadvantaged areas. This can affect the implementation of comprehensive teacher evaluation systems, including training evaluators and developing evaluation tools and procedures (Cagle, 2022). Ensuring teacher evaluation systems align with national educational standards and regulations while accommodating the diverse cultural and linguistic contexts within the Philippines can be complex. Striking the right balance is a continuous challenge. The Philippines has made significant strides in improving teacher quality, but challenges exist, such as providing ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers in remote areas. Recognizing and respecting the Philippines' diverse cultural backgrounds and indigenous knowledge systems is essential in teacher evaluation (Chu Bree, 2022). In Davao City, one of the major urban centers in the Philippines, there are specific challenges related to Teacher Evaluation Systems and their influence on Teacher Development. Davao City is known for its diverse population, including different ethnic groups and languages. Ensuring that teacher evaluation systems are sensitive to this diversity and promote inclusivity is a vital challenge. Urban schools often have higher student populations and may face issues related to teacher workload. Finding a balance between evaluation requirements and teachers' existing responsibilities is crucial. Addressing these challenges in Davao City may require tailored solutions that consider the unique urban context. It involves efforts to promote diversity, inclusivity, access to resources, and strategies for engaging with urban communities and fostering a culture of professional development and growth among teachers. Collaboration between the local government, educational institutions, and the community can be vital in addressing these challenges.

2. Methodology

Research methods were systematic processes used to collect and analyze data to answer research questions and address specific objectives. They were the foundation for empirical investigations in various fields, including science, social sciences, and humanities. Research methods encompass

a range of approaches, such as quantitative methods, which involve collecting numerical data through surveys, experiments, or statistical analysis, and qualitative methods, which focus on understanding and interpreting non-numerical data through interviews, content analysis, or ethnography. Researchers select methods based on the nature of their research questions and the type of data they need. The chosen methods guide data collection, analysis, and interpretation, ensuring that the research is rigorous and that the findings were reliable and valid. The choice of research method often depends on the study's goals, scope, and context, and researchers carefully select the most appropriate approach to address their research objectives.

2.1. Research Design—Non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs represent essential methods in the field of research, each with its distinct purpose and characteristics. Non-experimental research primarily focuses on observing and analyzing existing phenomena without manipulating variables. Descriptive research seeks to provide a comprehensive and detailed account of a particular situation, population, or event (Creswel, 2014). Correlational research, on the other hand, examines the relationships between variables, aiming to identify patterns, associations, or connections among them. It does not imply causation but helps researchers understand how changes in one variable may relate to changes in another. Predictive research design extends beyond describing and correlating variables. It involves developing models or theories to predict future outcomes or behavior. Researchers gather and analyze data to establish patterns that can be used for forecasting or making informed decisions. While these research designs serve distinct purposes, they share common advantages. They offer practicality, allowing researchers to study phenomena as they naturally occur, which was often the case in the social sciences. Non-experimental research designs are more ethical and logistically feasible when manipulation or experimentation is inappropriate or impossible. However, a limitation was the need for more control over variables, making it challenging to establish causal relationships. Non-experimental, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research designs are essential in quantitatively investigating teacher evaluation systems in private schools and their influence on teacher development. This study employs a non-experimental design to observe and collect data without manipulating variables, reflecting the natural state of teacher evaluation practices in private schools. Descriptive research provides a comprehensive portrayal of the existing teacher evaluation systems, detailing the various criteria and procedures in place. This approach aids in understanding the current landscape of teacher evaluations. Correlational research was valuable for identifying relationships and connections between the components of teacher evaluation systems and the subsequent teacher development outcomes. It helps to determine if and to what extent the two variables are associated. This is crucial in assessing the impact of these systems on teacher development. Furthermore, predictive research was used to ascertain whether the identified correlations could be used to predict or forecast teacher development outcomes. It allowed for the development of models or equations that could estimate the potential influence of teacher evaluation practices on teacher growth. In combination, these research designs enable a holistic and quantitative analysis of teacher evaluation systems' impact on teacher development in private schools, providing valuable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers seeking to improve educational practices in these institutions.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Private School Teach-

ers in the Davao City Schools area. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 120 teacher-respondents were taken randomly from the private schools surrounding the City. After being selected through randomization, respondents were notified both through online platforms and in-person, taking into account the availability of Wi-Fi connections. Additionally, they received an orientation regarding the study's objectives and its significance to their professional development. The selection of respondents was based on the assumption that they are actively managing and supervising schools in terms of organizational management and instructional supervision. They were expected to have a strong engagement with the curriculum implementation policy and pedagogical classroom activities, as well as the day-to-day management and execution of various school-based learning programs, projects, and activities designed to enhance early learners' development within the framework of private school management. The qualifications for participation in this study were rooted in the expectation that they had made significant contributions, extending beyond their primary roles in curriculum delivery, implementation, and governance, by actively participating in various educational activities. These contributions were typically discussed during school faculty meetings, group sessions, and committee meetings, all to improve the school environment and learners' educational experiences during the new normal learning system in the academic year 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data

collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—The instrument employed in this research study was meticulously crafted through a comprehensive review of existing literature and related studies. The researcher dedicated substantial effort to gathering and analyzing relevant literature, extracting key concepts that guided the instrument's development and fortified its alignment with the designated strands. This thorough procedure contributed to creating a well-structured set of questionnaire items, thereby bolstering the overall validity of the instrument and mitigating potential challenges to its reliability. As the authors argued, items were adapted from the reviewed literature. The survey questionnaire had two parts, each consisting of indicators of a teacher evaluation system regarding classroom observations, student achievement, professional conduct, use of technology, and specialized skills. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured teacher development regarding published work and research, coursework and advanced degrees, leadership service roles, and awards and recognition. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.896, which means that 89.6 percent level of confidence in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant, 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of the teacher evaluation system. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation were provided below:

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The statements provide a clear overview of the se-

quential steps that define the data collection process. This approach was vital to ensure safety

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teacher evaluation system is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teacher evaluation system is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teacher evaluation system is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teacher evaluation system is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teacher evaluation system is not manifested

and mitigate any potential risks associated with gathering relevant data, especially given the current context of ongoing in-person interactions. Permission to conduct the study. In the second week of December 2023, the researcher initiated the process of conceptualizing the content and objectives of the thesis proposal. Subsequently, she prepared various documents, including request letters, for the study. The research study strictly adhered to established ethical data collection procedures, as Creswell (2004) outlined, and followed the health protocols mandated by the IATF’s policy. As the research proposal was approved by the panel of members and the college dean in the last week of February to the first week of March 2024, the researcher composed and submitted a formal letter seeking permission to collect data and conduct the study within Davao City to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, following the proper channels. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In March 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet

form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents who do not have access to the internet. Likewise, a hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, a link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the Schools Division Superintendent approved the proceeding with data gathering, which commenced the third week of March 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of April 2024. For coaching and statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study sometime during the first week of April 2024 and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results during the second week of May 2024.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number

one (1) regarding the extent of the teacher evaluation system and statement problem number two (2) regarding the extent of teacher devel-

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation

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1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teacher development is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teacher development is not manifested

opment. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between teacher evaluation system and teacher development. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4 on the indicators of teacher evaluation systems

that significantly influence teacher development (Pallant, 2000) (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey’s Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were obtained, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the researcher addresses the collection of data and its subsequent presentation, analysis, and interpretation. Tabular and textual formats are employed to enhance the depth of analysis and facilitate the extraction of meaningful implications. Further, these presentations serve as supporting evidence for the hypothesis put forth.

Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of teacher evaluation systems. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: professional conduct (3.44) is oftentimes manifested; student achievement (3.10) and specialized skills (3.04)

are sometimes manifested; classroom evaluation (2.52) and use of technology (2.44) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.90 denotes the extent of work engagement, which is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive.

The results of teacher evaluations inform decisions related to professional development, teacher retention, promotion, compensation, and other personnel management aspects. The core objective of teacher evaluation systems is to maintain and enhance the quality of education by identifying areas of strength and oppor-

tunities for improvement, thereby fostering a culture of continuous growth and development among educators. These systems are a critical tool for school administrators and policymakers in their efforts to deliver high-quality education. In current teacher evaluation systems, the two main purposes of evaluation accountability/goal

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Teacher Evaluation Systems

No	Teacher Evaluation Systems	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Classroom Evaluation	2.52	Less Extensive
2	Student Achievement	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	Professional Conduct	3.44	Extensive
4	Use of Technology	2.44	Less Extensive
5	Specialized Skills	3.04	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		2.90	Moderately Extensive

accomplishment (summative) and professional growth/improvement (formative) are often at odds with one another. However, they are not only compatible but linking them within a unified teacher evaluation system is desirable. The challenge of the next generation of teacher evaluation systems is to integrate these two purposes in policy and practice. Ford and Hewitt (2020) integrate the frameworks of Self-determination theory and Stronge’s Improvement-Oriented Model for Performance Evaluation to critically examine teacher evaluation policy in Hawaii and Washington, D.C.—two distinctly different approaches to teacher evaluation to identify a set of clear recommendations for improving the design and implementation of teacher evaluation policy moving forward.

Summary of the Extent of Teacher Development

Table 2 shows the summary of the extent of teacher development. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: coursework and advanced degrees (3.72), awards and recognition (3.68), and leadership and service roles (3.52) are oftentimes manifested, while published work and research (2.44) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.34 denotes the extent of work engagement is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The goal of teacher development is to ensure that educators stay current with best practices, adapt to changing educational trends, and meet the diverse learning needs of their students. Ultimately, teacher development contributes to better student outcomes, a more dynamic and engaging learning environment, and the overall advancement of education.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Teacher Development

No	Teacher Development	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Published Work and Research	2.44	Less Extensive
2	Coursework and Advanced Degrees	3.72	Extensive
3	Leadership and Service Roles	3.52	Extensive
4	Awards and Recognition	3.68	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.34	Moderately Extensive

Schliemann et.al. (2022) report on a teacher development program aimed at improving mathematics teaching and learning from grades 5-9. The program employed functions as a lens to reinterpret and interconnect content topics in the mathematics curriculum. It was designed to promote a deep understanding of mathematics while drawing upon students' spontaneous reasoning, generalizations, representations, and discussions about relations between physical quantities and numbers. Results suggest that the teacher development program contributed to improved teaching in the target districts and to positive changes in the performance of target district students on state-mandated tests. An important educational goal for the next generation is the ability to think computationally. However, if students' learning outcomes were not assessed, it is not known whether the enhancement of teacher capacity could impact on students' learning. Kong and Lai (2023) aimed to examine how a teacher development program changed teachers' content knowledge and collaborative engagement, which in turn influenced their students' learning achievement. The teach-

ers' content knowledge and collaborative engagement were significantly enhanced through the program, which significantly impacted student achievement. Teachers' years of teaching experience, but not their gender or whether they had majored in computer science, could also affect student achievement. The results indicate that a teacher development program can significantly enhance the teachers' CT content knowledge and collaborative engagement, which can positively affect student learning.

Significant Relationship between Teacher Evaluation Systems and Teacher Development

Table 3 revealed the significant relationship between teachers' psychological safety and work engagement. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis, stating that there is no significant relationship between teachers' psychological safety and work engagement, must be rejected, for it provided empirical evidence to show its correlation. It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teacher evaluation systems ($r=0.878$; $p<.000$) and teacher development.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Teacher Evaluation Systems and Teacher Development

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Teacher Development	0.868	<0.000	Significant	Reject H0

**significant @ $p<0.05$.*

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he significant relationship between teacher evaluation systems and teacher development underscores the assessment processes' pivotal role in shaping and enhancing educators' professional growth. Schliemann et al. (2022) report that teacher evaluation systems provide a structured framework for assessing performance, identifying strengths, and pinpointing

areas for improvement. When implemented effectively, these systems contribute to a culture of continuous improvement by offering constructive feedback and fostering reflective practices (Williams and Hebert, 2020). Chu and Bree (2022) identify targeted feedback from evaluations; teachers gain valuable insights into their instructional practices, enabling them to refine

their teaching techniques and adapt to evolving educational standards. Moreover, teacher evaluation systems often serve as a foundation for personalized professional development plans, aligning resources and support to specific needs identified through assessments. Temel and Gür (2022) said that this symbiotic relationship between evaluation and development creates a cycle of improvement, promoting a culture of accountability and excellence within the teaching profession. As teacher evaluation systems evolve, it becomes crucial to prioritize a balanced approach that holds educators accountable and supports their ongoing development, ensuring a collaborative and growth-oriented educational environment.

Domains of Teacher Evaluation Systems Significantly Influence Teacher Development

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coeffi-

cient analysis on domains of teacher evaluation systems that significantly influence teacher development. Domains of teacher evaluation systems in terms of classroom evaluation (0.000), student achievement (0.000), professional conduct (0.002), use of technology (0.000), and specialized skills (0.000) significantly influenced teacher development. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.857 suggests that 85.7 of teacher evaluation systems can explain teacher development. This provides empirical evidence that teacher evaluation systems can account for and explain teacher development variability. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (264.576) and F-statistic are significant $p < .000$, which tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of teacher development.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Teacher Evaluation Systems Significantly Influence Teacher Development

Model	B	Beta		Standard Error		p-value	Decisions
H(Intercept)	4.145	0.079		60.416	0.001	4.143	
H(Intercept)	0.313	0.175		1.066	0.270	0.201	
classroom evaluation	0.817	0.117	0.101	1.010	0.315	0.000	*Reject H0
student achievement	0.431	0.118	0.132	1.275	0.196	0.000	*Reject H0
professional conduct	0.212	0.097	0.211	2.086	0.038	0.002	*Reject H0
use of technology	0.921	0.508	0.136	1.259	0.296	0.000	*Reject H0
specialized skills	0.502	0.057	0.210	3.068	0.038	0.000	*Reject H0

R2 = 0.857

F-value = 264.576

p-value = <0.000

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

Teacher evaluation systems significantly influence teacher development, playing a crucial role in shaping educators' professional growth. Bleiberg et al. (2020) examine that these systems serve as a structured mechanism for assessing teaching performance, offering valuable insights into instructional practices, classroom management, and overall effectiveness. When designed thoughtfully, evaluations provide teachers with constructive feedback, identifying areas of strength and areas that require improvement. This feedback becomes a catalyst for targeted professional development initiatives. Teachers, as Hanushek et al. (2020) use, armed with a clear understanding of their

strengths and areas for growth, can engage in purposeful learning experiences tailored to their specific needs. Effective teacher evaluation systems, therefore, act as a catalyst for ongoing teacher development, creating a continuous cycle of assessment, feedback, and improvement. Kim and Sun (2021) draw to maximize the positive impact on teacher development, it is essential for evaluation processes to be fair, transparent, and focused on fostering a collaborative and supportive learning environment. This approach ensures that teacher development is not merely an outcome of evaluations but an integral part of a broader commitment to enhancing the overall quality of education.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analysis, discussions, and drawing of implications. Findings were based on the problem's statement; conclusions were based on the findings generated, and recommendations were based on the impact of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following were the study's findings, as shown in the presentation results, analysis, and discussions. The extent of teacher evaluation systems in terms of professional conduct (3.44) was oftentimes manifested; student achievement (3.10) and specialized skills (3.04) were sometimes manifested; classroom evaluation (2.52) and use of technology (2.44) were rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.90 denotes the extent of work engagement, which was sometimes manifested; thus, it was moderately extensive. The extent of teacher development in terms of coursework and advanced degrees (3.72), awards and recognition (3.68), and leadership and service roles (3.52) were oftentimes manifested, while published work and research (2.44) was rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.34 denotes the extent of work engagement that was sometimes manifested; thus, it was moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a

significant correlation between teacher evaluation systems ($r=0.878$; $p<.000$) and teacher development. Domains of teacher evaluation systems in terms of classroom evaluation (0.000), student achievement (0.000), professional conduct (0.002), use of technology (0.000), and specialized skills (0.000) significantly influenced teacher development.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were the conclusions to wit; The extent of teacher evaluation systems in terms of professional conduct was often manifested; student achievement and specialized skills were sometimes manifested; classroom evaluation and use of technology were rarely manifested. The extent of work engagement was sometimes manifested; thus, it was moderately extensive. The extent of teacher development in terms of coursework and advanced degrees, awards and recognition, and leadership and service roles were oftentimes

manifested, while published work and research are rarely manifested. The extent of work engagement is sometimes manifested, thus moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teacher evaluation systems and teacher development. Domains of teacher evaluation systems in terms of classroom evaluation, student achievement, professional conduct, use of technology, and specialized skills (0.000) significantly influenced teacher development.

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May invest in comprehensive training programs for administrators responsible for conducting teacher evaluations to ensure a fair and consistent approach. Encourage the integration of qualitative and quantitative measures in evaluation systems to provide a more holistic view of teacher performance. Advocate for a collaborative culture that promotes ongoing communication between supervisors and teachers, fostering a supportive environment for professional growth. School Principal. May implement evaluation systems that emphasize constructive feedback and recog-

nize teachers' strengths alongside areas for improvement. Establish a clear connection between evaluation outcomes and professional development opportunities, creating tailored plans to address specific needs identified during assessments. Foster a positive school culture that values continuous learning and encourages teachers to engage in their professional development actively. Teacher. May embrace the feedback received through evaluations as opportunities for growth rather than solely as assessments of performance. Take an active role in identifying areas for professional development and collaborate with administrators to create personalized development plans. Advocate for a supportive school culture where teachers feel empowered to seek assistance and engage in continuous learning. Future Researcher. May explore the long-term impact of different teacher evaluation systems on overall teacher development and student outcomes. Investigate the effectiveness of various professional development models in response to specific needs identified through teacher evaluations. Examine the influence of contextual factors, such as school culture and leadership, on the relationship between teacher evaluations and subsequent development.

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